

DATA4CIRC

Data-driven AI-assisted Digital Framework for Enhancing Circularity in Manufacturing

www.data4circ.eu

Funded by
the European Union

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Project Coordinator: IDENER.AI

Communications: EIT Manufacturing East GmbH

Partners

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